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The importance of communication factors in the innovation process and the potential Turkey's example in Azerbaijan

Abstract

Although the process of creating an innovation ecosystem in Turkey takes about 20 years, this process is in the commencement period in Azerbaijan. On the other hand, the sustainability of these countries in the innovation process should be taken into consideration which based on commercial or economic rules. In other words, the commercial culture here must be taken into account in order to create the innovation ecosystem in any country. In this research, Turkey's experience in the innovation process, communication problems of Turkey and Azerbaijan in the innovation ecosystem and ways to overcome these problems will be explained. At the end of the research, some recommendations will be made on the possibilities of implementing Turkey's experience in Azerbaijan, the situation analysis of some communication problems in Turkey and Azerbaijan economies, as well.

Key words: Innovation process, communication factors, economics, Turkey experience

Introduction

Right after the industrial revolution, economic perspectives which is based on knowledge is one of the most up-to-date topics in the world. Globalization and competitiveness are the further development of the knowledge economy in the world economy. In this process, industrial society has also given its place to the information society. This process has become much faster, especially in developed countries. Thus, developed countries increase the amount of capital investment in knowledge-based fields to become a larger shareholder in the world markets. As it is seen the competition has increased and continues to grow. To generate innovation in the competitive environment is one of the most efficient ways for achieving higher economic results. Thus, the locomotive role is derived from innovation studies in knowledge-based economies. The impact of globalization and higher technological developments drive enterprises into an economical competition. Enterprises should have a competitive-based strategy to maintain their assets in the long run and achieve sustainable competitive advantage.

Innovation provides a better level of individual and social needs (health, rest, work, transportation, etc.). Innovation is also essential for the entrepreneurial spirit because a certain innovation may bring every new venture comes to the end of the process successfully. Moreover, all ventures need constant revival in order to maintain their competitiveness. This is true for countries as well. In order to maintain their economic growth, competitiveness, and employment opportunities, countries have to transform their ideas into rapid, technical and commercial success. [1]. Although the process of creating an innovation ecosystem takes about 20 years in Turkey, this process is new in Azerbaijan. The main thing, commercial culture here must be taken into account in order to create the innovation ecosystem. Belonging to the same nation, thus the commercial and economic culture of the Azerbaijani population is very close to the commercial and economic culture of the Turkish population. Whether cultural proximity, geographical proximity or innovation work, Azerbaijan can be

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achieved higher results from innovation process with the study of the experience of Turkey. Additionally, the case of Turkey might be implemented in Azerbaijan. In this research, Turkey's experience in the innovation process, communication problems of Azerbaijan and Turkey in the innovation ecosystem and ways to overcome these problems will be learned. As a result of the research, recommendations will be given about the possibilities of implementing Turkey experience in Azerbaijan, the situation analysis of some communication problems in Turkey and Azerbaijan economies, as well.

What is the innovation process and how does it occur

What is innovation and its types

Besides its productivity, innovation is a service that can be sold. Hence, innovation does not have to be an invention. (Innovation can be a new invention or not). Varieties of innovations that are positioned in different fields and situations can be classified as follows: [2]

Innovation Type	Example:
Product Innovation	New or improved products (cell phones, internet-enabled mobile phones)
Process Innovation	A new production method (flotel glass production)
Organizational Innovation	A new internal communication system (intranet) is a new costing system
Production Management Innovation	Quality circles, full-time production, new production planning system, new quality control system
Commercial / Marketing Innovation	New sales techniques, new financial methods (risk capital)
Service Innovation	Internet banking, patient admissions system

Innovation process and its importance

Innovation or its diversity can be more and more effective as a result of specific researches and a well-developed ecosystem. Innovative ecosystems (USA, Japan, South Korea, European countries, India, China, etc.), which are good examples in the world, prove the need to have an importance of intense cooperation and productive communication. It is impossible to create an ecosystem without co-operation. Effective co-operation is possible through efficient operation of communication factors.

We can say that innovation and wealth are directly linked. There are many factors that determine a country's innovation capacity. Individual skills, entrepreneurial support and public support are not sufficient for innovation. Innovation is an ecosystem work. In the case of United States, which is one of the leading countries in the field of innovation, we see that public policy, co-operative environment, academies, entrepreneurial quality, financial funding capacity, tolerance environment, national market depth, and all other components are main keypoints for innovation.[3]. Innovation usually occurs in a four-step process: [4]

- a. Defining the problem (the subject);
- b. Creating creative ideas and solutions;
- c. Evaluation and selection of ideas;
- d. Projecting and implementation (dissemination to the company or customer service)

Innovative process models may also be available in the different ecosystem and market conditions. The innovation process model presented by Müfit Akyos as an effective model (based on the works of J. Clark and K. Guy, 1997) is as above:

One of the most important factors in the innovation process is to maintain R & D work effectively. The role of institutions that carry out university or scientific studies in the process of innovation is also significant. It is known that these institutions have innovative approaches and their attitudes towards the market demands are very important. University-industry co-operation allows the countries to find scientific and technological research into a product or service, a new or improved manufacturing or distribution method, and new social service method. From this perspective, university-industry co-operation is one of the most critical rings of the innovation ecosystem. In fact, the existence of many other elements of the innovation ecosystem as technoparks is intended to create the most appropriate environment for this cooperation. [5]

Nowadays, compared businesses, which are dependent on resource availability and low cost advantages, lost their power. Countries which wish to increase their national competitiveness need to reach a high competitive edge of competitiveness based on their high R & D intensity, high innovation skills and high value added. States need to maintain the sustainable growth based on political and economic stability, make adequate investment in human resources, and support R & D activities. The concepts of development, and prosperity are closely related to the production and implementation of technological knowledge. Technological information can only be obtained as a result of research and development activities. Countries that have already started the work of understanding the information society are now called developed countries. [6] As mentioned above, economic approaches that based on information or knowledge is one of the most up-to-date issues in the world after the industrial revolution.

Communication factors in the process of innovation

As it is stated, innovation appears as a result of a process. While explaining the definition of innovation, we see that there is innovation on the basis of the concept. This situation indicates that innovation requires a new approach, a new perspective, a new expansion or a different effect. On the other hand, innovation should be productive and applicable. In addition, innovation has to be a product or service that can be sold. Hence, innovation has been pursuing every aspect of today's life, which does not remain indifferent to the community. Individuals do not notice whether they are innovators or consumers, society they are influenced or affected by this process.

Innovation is directly responsible for the economy because it has a different product or service with its adaptability. The innovation and innovation process currently affects the economy in local or macro forms. Thus, it is possible to say that the rapid development of technology and innovation is a prerequisite for entrepreneurial activity and competitive environment. In addition, innovation also requires R & D that based on regular and research-driven research results. In other words, innovation requires the need for training and research. This situation, as well as social existence, connects individuals and societies as long as possible.

Commercialization and innovation of scientific breakdown results are currently considered the most important competitive force. Innovative competitive advantages are more important for firms. [8] The various aspects of society are involved in different forms, influencing the process in the innovative world. For example, an innovative solution based on university research and scientific work can be the basis for productivity in the industry. However, if there is no good communication between the industrialist and the academician, the adaptation of the innovative production in the industry can either be impossible or take longer. Innovation should be adaptable. When universities do not collaborate with industrialists while preparing workers who they need in the business world, it is certain that they will not be able to deal with market problems on time. However, if the value generation is not marketed, the continuity of the process will not be effective. It has been argued that the feasibility of the added value is even more effective with the strong communication of the stakeholders. Information society, which is active nowadays, and increases the scope of communication. It is almost impossible to create information society without communication.

The innovation process or innovation activities are important in problem solving that is becoming even more serious in the today's world. Thus, one of the most important factors in innovation is entrepreneurship. It is true that innovation allows effective work which is done with the integration of information technologies and fewer employees. But this does not adversely affect the employment of the world in general. The emergence of new ventures and the closure of less productive firms are key factors that enhance the dynamism of modern economies. In addition to improving the quality of production and service, innovation improves economic situation by reducing costs, improving quality and providing other options. On the other hand, the innovation process offers entrepreneurship opportunities, allowing individuals to build their own business or innovate with greater tension and power. The impact of entrepreneurial approaches in different countries is also strongly linked to the social status of the population.

As a result, we can define the importance of affinity factors in the innovation process:

Interconnection between the parties is one of the most important factors in the innovation process. Therefore, without good communication between the parties, neither innovation nor economic development can be improved. In free market conditions, the parties (state, university, academician, entrepreneur, student, individual, etc.) can achieve positive results by creating added value in their economic interests. Communities that can create such a communication ecosystem and social well-being of the population. Thus, the cooperation and communication factors are important for the development of innovation ecosystems that can provide development in the long run.

Current situation and perspectives in innovation studies in Azerbaijan

The Republic of Azerbaijan, whose economy is essentially based on the oil industry, is launching large-scale projects for integrating into the global economy, with its own economic strategies and globalization demands. There is no foreign exchange gain in return for value added in the country's economy, because oil exported in the form of raw materials. Numerous

decisions have been made and projects have been initiated under the policy of "the oil capital should be transformed into human capital" by President İlham Aliyev. But due to the lack of intellectual human capital, it is impossible to effectively utilize high technology, which has been implanted in the country. In order to ensure the competitiveness of the domestic market, the rapid development of innovation and entrepreneurship is needed. Therefore, systems need to be studied and applied to the experiences in order to be effective in the short and long run projects. Turkey is one of the closest countries in terms of trade, economic, political, cultural and education for Azerbaijan. Cooperation projects in Azerbaijan's largest economic areas are being carried out with Turkey. In addition to commercial and cultural affiliations, geographical proximity also increases the likelihood that single projects can become more productive in innovation and entrepreneurship.

In recent years, some large-scale decisions or projects for the creation and development of ecosystems in the fields of high technology, innovation and agrarianism in Azerbaijan can be listed as follows:

- In accordance with Article 109, paragraph 32, of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, "For the purpose of establishing modern information technologies for sustainable development and competitiveness of the economy, expansion of the scope of information and communication technologies based on modern scientific and technological achievements, scientific research and development of new information technologies" The decision of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated 5 November 2012 on the establishment of the Highest Technology Park. [10]
- "Azerbaijan 2020: Outlook for the Future" Development Concept, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated 29 December 2012. [11]
- National Strategy for Development of Information Society In The Republic Of Azerbaijan for the 2014-2020. Decision of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan of April 2, 2014. [12]
- "Principles on Technology Parks" was approved by the Presidential Decree of 15 May 2014. [13]
- To ensure the intellectual, physical and spiritual development of young people in the socio-economic, socio-political and cultural life of the country, in accordance with Article 32 and Article 109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, dated January 26, 2015, Young People's Strategy ". [14]
- In accordance with paragraphs 1 and 10 of Article 94 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the basic principles of the state policy in the organization, management and development of scientific activities in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the purpose of science and scientific-innovation activities, the organizational and legal bases of their use, the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Science, Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan of 9 August 2016, defining and promoting the mechanisms, the promotion and use of scientific achievements. [15]
- "Strategic Roadmap for Azerbaijan's National Economy Perspectives" Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated December 6, 2016. [16]
- "State Youth Program in Azerbaijan 2017-2021", Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated 15 September 2017. [17]
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on June 26, 2018 on the establishment of the "Small and Medium Business Development Agency in

Azerbaijan" to ensure the development of small and medium-sized enterprises in Azerbaijan. [18]

As it is seen, important decisions have been made in Azerbaijan for the establishment of the economy within the innovation process. Research and learning of world samples are of great importance for the implementation of these decisions and continuous development of competition. As mentioned above, research and coordination of the Turkey examples can give positive results in Azerbaijan economy for the innovation process, the improvement of educational and research institutions.

Result

- Innovation production and its adaptation are inevitable for a strong and sustainable economy in the contemporary era where competitiveness deepens and faster. This applies both to firms and to the country's economy; It is important to function efficiently in the innovation process or to create an ecological innovation ecosystem for the communication process;
- It is important to work efficiently for the communication process in the innovation process or to create an ecological innovation ecosystem. In other words, innovation or innovation process is essentially important for different parties to provide their own needs more efficiently. Communicating with those involved in the innovation process can lead to added value in line with the needs of the stakeholders. The risks of innovation can increase if the factors of communication do not work well.
- The process of creating an innovation ecosystem in Turkey can be considered as approximately 15 years after Azerbaijan. This means that Turkey has more experience in similar institutions on communication than Azerbaijan. Experiences gained during the process are worth learning and can provide good results in similar economies, especially in Azerbaijan. Faster development of innovation work, and the sharing of acquired knowledge and experience are considered to be one of the key factors. From this perspective, it can be said that the process of learning or researching the experience of Turkey in similar economies can also provide efficient results for Turkey itself.
- Important decisions have been made for the establishment of an innovation ecosystem in Azerbaijan, and Azerbaijan needs expertise in this area. Learning the knowledge and experience quickly can be more efficient than its reproduction. In this sense, it can be useful to explore and learn Turkey's example for the establishment and development of innovation ecosystem in Azerbaijan.
- Investigating Turkey's example for the establishment of innovation ecosystem in Azerbaijan especially in the implementation of the communication factors in the process of innovation, can provide useful results. Thus, Turkey and Azerbaijan have very close values according to national and entrepreneurial characteristics. Additionally, geographical proximity and political-economic outreach can lead to rapid and efficient developments in their innovation process.

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Kommunikasiya amillərinin innovasiya prosesində əhəmiyyəti və Türkiyənin
Azərbaycanda potensial nümunəsi

Xülasə

Türkiyədə innovasiya ekosisteminin yaradılması prosesi təxminən 20 il çəksə də, Azərbaycanda bu proses ilkin mərhələdədir. Digər tərəfdən, bu ölkələrin kommersiya və ya iqtisadi qaydalara əsaslanan innovasiya prosesində dayanıqlığını nəzərə almaq lazımdır. Başqa sözlə, istənilən ölkədə innovasiya ekosisteminin yaradılması üçün kommersiya mədəniyyətini nəzərə almaq lazımdır. Bu araşdırmada Türkiyənin innovasiya prosesində təcrübəsi, innovativ ekosistemdə Türkiyə və Azərbaycanın kommunikasiya problemləri və bu problemlərin aradan qaldırılması yolları izah edilir. Tədqiqatın nəticələrinə görə, Türkiyənin Azərbaycanda təcrübəsinin reallaşdırılması imkanları, Türkiyə və Azərbaycan iqtisadiyyatında bəzi kommunikasiya problemlərinin situasiya təhlili ilə bağlı bəzi tövsiyələr verilir.

Açar sözlər: innovasiya prosesi, kommunikasiya amilləri, iqtisadiyyat, Türkiyə təcrübəsi

İса Касумов, Енсар Локманоглу, Анар Рза
Важность коммуникационных факторов в инновационном процессе и
потенциальный пример Турции в Азербайджане

Резюме

Хотя процесс создания инновационной экосистемы в Турции занимает около 20 лет, в Азербайджане этот процесс находится в начальном периоде. С другой стороны, следует учитывать устойчивость этих стран в инновационном процессе, которая основывается на коммерческих или экономических правилах. Иными словами, для создания инновационной экосистемы в любой стране необходимо учитывать коммерческую культуру. В данном исследовании будет объяснен опыт Турции в инновационном процессе, коммуникационные проблемы Турции и Азербайджана в инновационной экосистеме и пути преодоления этих проблем. По итогам исследования будут даны некоторые рекомендации относительно возможностей реализации опыта Турции в Азербайджане, ситуационного анализа некоторых коммуникационных проблем в экономике Турции и Азербайджана.

Ключевые слова: инновационный процесс, коммуникационные факторы, экономика, опыт Турции

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